

D6.4 Data management plan

Name of project: [Fostering high scientific quality in protein research in Eastern Slovakia \(CasProt\)](#)
No. 952333

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Deliverable No:	D.6.4.
Work package no. and title	WP6 Management
Task no. and title:	6.3.: Quality assurance and risk management
Nature:	ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot
Dissemination level:	Public
Lead Beneficiary:	UPJS
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Date of updated publication:	2 May 2022

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ABBREVIATIONS

AAM/VoR	Author accepted manuscript/version of record (VOR)
API	Application Programming Interface
CA	Consortium Agreement
COAR	Confederation of Open Access Repositories
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of the Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DoS attack	Denial-of-service attack
DoW	The Description of Work
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	The European Research Area
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
GB	Gigabyte
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2020	Horizon 2020
I4OC	Initiative for Open Citations
IPR	Intellectual property rights
ISBN	International Standard Book Number
JATS	Journal Article Tag Suite
OAI-PMH	The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OpenAIRE	European Open Science Infrastructure, for open scholarly and scientific communication.
OpenDOAR	Directory of Open Access Repositories
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
SPDX	Software Package Data Exchange
PDF	Portable Data File
PID	A persistent identifier
PMC	PubMed Central®
TUM	Technical University of Munich
UI	User Interface
UPJS	Univerzita Pavla Jozefa Šafárika v Košiciach
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
URN	Uniform Resource Name
UZ	Universität Zürich
WP	Work Package XML
	Extensible Markup Language

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Here we report the first version of the CasProt Data Management Plan (DMP), which defines the data handling processes during the project. CasProt generates several data types that are stored during the project lifespan. After the project's end, we will support the storage and re-usability of the project data. We have decided that data will be stored in the Zenodo repository platform, which fulfills mandatory as well as highly recommended criteria for data repositories. It is expected that during the project, the partnership with EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) will be established and going into operation. In this case, it is expected that all scientific data generated by the CasProt project will be managed, stored, standardized, registered, and cataloged by EOSC rules.

The CasProt project participates in a pilot action on open research data. The aim is to provide indications as to what kind of data the project will collect, how the data will be preserved, and which sharing policies will be adopted towards making these data readily available to the research community. The project's efforts in the area of open research data are outlined, giving particular awareness to the following issues: *(i)* the types of open and non-open data that will be generated or collected by the Consortium, via experimental work and research, related to the project; *(ii)* The standards used to encrypt the data; *(iii)* the technologies and infrastructures used to preserve the data long-term securely; *(iv)* the sharing/access policies are applied to each dataset. The plan can be considered as a blueprint for the future and as a benchmark for the resource and budget allocations related to data management. As the project unfolds, the present DMP will be upgraded according to the Consortium's needs. At any time, the DMP will reflect the current state of the Consortium's agreements regarding data management, utilization, and protection of rights and results.

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1. INTRODUCTION: BACKGROUND AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

One of the projected impacts of the Open Research Data Pilot of the European Commission is to provide open access and re-use of research data that are produced by Horizon 2020 projects. To this end, two primary tools are used:

- 1) to develop a Data Management Plan (DMP), and
- 2) to provide open access to research data for general/public use.

Here, to implement the Pilot, our Consortium has to fulfill several partial tasks, including the development of the DMP, regular updating of the DMP, depositing data in a repository, enabling access to the data for other researchers/public, providing background information to work with primary data. The Pilot primarily concerns with two main items:

- a. The data (and metadata) that are required to validate outcomes in scientific publications.
- b. Other curated and/or raw data, including metadata

The DMP will function as a guiding document to ensure good data management throughout the lifecycle of the project in order to make the information collected and produced Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable (FAIR).

This DMP describes how data generated by the CasProt project are handled both throughout the project's lifespan and after the end of the project. DMP defines procedures and minimum requirements to gather, store, analyzed, and publish data in a consistent way according to the FAIR principles. DMP for the project CasProt was conceptually designed as a "living document" and will be updated when necessary. All project partners, TUM and UZ, will be noticed by email, which will summarize the changes made to this document. Common standards, folder structure, and identifiers will be defined by the authors of the DMP. Information will be made available via the internal information processes (minutes) and during the next General Assembly (GA) meeting. The DMP leading author will coordinate all email communication.

1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

A general objective of the CasProt project is to significantly strengthen the scientific excellence in protein science at the University of Pavol Jozef Safarik in Kosice by linking it with two internationally leading institutions from one EU Member State and one Associated

Country: Technical University of Munich (Germany) and University of Zürich (Switzerland). By means of short-term staff exchange, expert visits training, joint summer schools, workshops, and conference attendance, the following main objectives of the project will be reached:

- (1) **Reinforcement scientific capacity and raise the research profile of the coordinating institution-UPJS in the field of protein science.** The reinforcement of scientific capacity and the raise the research profile will take place in the field of protein science by taking advantage of the knowledge and know-how transfer to UPJS from the leading research European institutions who are partners in the project: University of Zurich, Switzerland, and the Technical University of Munich, Germany. Primarily, short-term expert visits and staff exchange will contribute to this goal.

- (2) **Identification and integration of the experienced and young/early-stage researchers into UPJS.** The identification and integration of the experienced, as well as young promising scientists/early stage researchers, will significantly improve research quality in interdisciplinary life sciences and related scientific areas in Slovakia. Moreover, the integration will lead to greater opportunities for UPJS to participate in various European and/or other international projects. This objective will be accomplished by their participation in the activities of the project (workshops, joint summer schools, short-term exchange visits). This objective helps UPJS to raise both the research profile of the institution and of its staff. In particular, we will strongly support early-stage researchers to maximize the benefit from know-how transfer and from the financial support of the CasProt Twinning project.

- (3) **Enhance and stimulate the technological capacity of the coordinating institution-UPJS.** This objective will be accomplished by the participation of the high-tech companies (e.g. SHIMADZU, Zeiss, Malvern) in the activities of the project (workshops and training, joint summer schools). The presence of the high-tech companies on the common activities of the project will enhance the technological capacity of the coordinating institution and potentiate the capability of UPJS to form strong connections with pharmaceutical and/or biotechnological companies within the field of biomedicine and protein science. The connection between UPJS, recognized international partners, and high - tech industry can lead to a submission of joint projects within Horizon Europe or other grant schemes and to the creation of new start-up companies in UPJS.

- (4) **Strengthening the research management and organizational skills at UPJS.** By means of short-term staff exchange and workshops we will utilize the experience and best practices of the experienced scientists, administration, and management staff of the University of

Zürich and Technical University of Munich for improving our capacity to prepare, coordinate, and manage scientific projects.

For **each objective**, specific requirements of data collection/generation are needed and are reported in the table below.

Table 1.

MAIN OBJECTIVES	DATA COLLECTION/GENERATION	WP
1) Reinforcement scientific capacity and raise the research profile of the coordinating institution UPJS in the field of protein science.	<input type="checkbox"/> Original research publications <input type="checkbox"/> Report on Protein stability and folding <input type="checkbox"/> Report on Directed evolution of proteins	WP1
2) Identification and integration of the experienced and young scientists/early-stage researchers into UPJS.	<input type="checkbox"/> Protein stability and folding proceedings <input type="checkbox"/> Directed evolution of proteins proceedings <input type="checkbox"/> Handouts from the individual lecturers and training experts Presentations, <input type="checkbox"/> Posters <input type="checkbox"/> Handouts from the individual lecturers and training experts	WP2 WP3
3) Enhance and stimulate the technological capacity of the coordinating institution UPJS	<input type="checkbox"/> Description of Work (DoW), publishable results achieved in other work packages, discussions, workshops, etc. <input type="checkbox"/> Questionnaire on the potential commercial impact of our research. This questionnaire will be sent to various potential business partners with the aim of revealing their interest in collaborating on the commercialization of our products.	WP1 WP4
4) Strengthening the research management and organizational skills at UPJS	<input type="checkbox"/> Description of Work (DoW), publishable results achieved in other work packages, discussions, workshops, etc. <input type="checkbox"/> Guide for preparation administration and management of EU project for UPJS staff <input type="checkbox"/> Best practice recommendation from UZ and TUM <input type="checkbox"/> Manual for UPJS staff "How to write successful proposals for European projects <input type="checkbox"/> Project quality plan <input type="checkbox"/> Quality assurance and risk analysis reports (M6) <input type="checkbox"/> Data management plan	WP5 WP6

1.2 What types of data will the project generate/collect?

CasProt objectives will produce text data with embedded images from secondary sources (see Table 1). At the same time, CasProt will exploit existing data and integrate them with new data. Table 1 shows the primary data on which it will exploit.

1.3 What formats of data will the project generate/collect?

By default, data will be stored in Portable Data File (pdf) format. Database, notes, and other data can be stored in other formats that are readable by MS Office tools and their open versions.

1.4 What is the origin of the data?

Data are from both primary and secondary sources.

1.5 What is the expected size of the data?

The expected overall data size is <100 GB.

1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Data utility is summarized in the following Table.

Table 2. Data primarily generated by the CasProt project.*Text with embedded images

DATA	TYPE/FORMAT	TARGET GROUPS	AVAILABILITY
Original research publications	Text*/pdf	Researchers	Open access
Report on Protein stability and folding	Text*/ pdf	Researchers	Free

Report on Directed evolution of proteins	Text*/pdf	Researchers	Free
Protein stability and folding proceedings	Text*/pdf	Ph.D. students	Free
Directed evolution of proteins proceedings	Text*/pdf	PhD. students	Free
Handouts from the individual lecturers and training experts	Text*/pdf	Ph.D. students	Free
Presentations, Posters	Text*/pdf	Consortium members	Free
Description of Work	Text*/pdf	Consortium members	Free
Questionnaire on the potential commercial impact of our research	Text*/pdf	Consortium members	Confidential
Guide for preparation administration and management of EU project for UPJS staff	Text*/pdf	UPJS staff	Free
Project quality plan	Text*/pdf	Consortium members	Free
Quality assurance and risk analysis reports	Text*/pdf	Consortium members	Confidential
Data management plan	Text*/pdf	Researchers	Free

2. FAIR DATA

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?

For our repository, we have decided to use Zenodo. Zenodo is a general-purpose open access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It allows researchers to deposit research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and other research-related digital artifacts. For each submission, a persistent digital object identifier (DOI) is minted, which makes the stored items easily citeable. Zenodo follows FAIR principles.

To be Findable:

F1: (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier

- DOI is issued to every published record on Zenodo,

F2: data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)

- Zenodo's metadata is compliant with DataCite's Metadata Schema minimum and recommended terms, with a few additional enrichments,

F3: metadata clearly and explicitly includes the identifier of the data it describes.

- The DOI is a top-level and mandatory field in the metadata of each record. F4: (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource
- The metadata of each record is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing.
- Metadata of each record is sent to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed there.

To be Accessible:

A1: (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol

- Metadata for individual records and record collections are harvestable using the OAIPMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name.
- Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API. A1.1: the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
- See point A1. OAI-PMH and REST are open, free, and universal protocols for information retrieval on the web.

A1.2: the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
 ☐ Metadata is publicly accessible and licensed under the public domain. No authorization is ever necessary to retrieve it.

A2: metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

- Data and metadata will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which presently has an experimental program defined for the next 20 years at least.
- Metadata is stored in high-availability database servers at CERN, which is separate from the data itself.

To be Interoperable:

I1: (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.

- Zenodo uses JSON Schema as an internal representation of metadata and offers export to other popular formats such as Dublin Core or MARCXML.

I2: (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles

- For certain terms, we refer to open, external vocabularies, e.g., license (Open Definition), funders (FundRef), and grants (OpenAIRE).

I3: (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

- Each referenced external piece of metadata is qualified by a resolvable URL.

To be Reusable:

R1: (meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes

- Each record contains a minimum of DataCite's mandatory terms, with optionally additional DataCite, recommended terms, and Zenodo's enrichments.

R1.1: (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license

- License is one of the mandatory terms in Zenodo's metadata and is referring to an Open Definition license.
- Data downloaded by the users are subject to the license specified in the metadata by the uploader.

R1.2: (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance

- All data and metadata uploaded are traceable to a registered Zenodo user.
- Metadata can optionally describe the original authors of the published work.

R1.3: (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

- Zenodo is not a domain-specific repository, yet through compliance with DataCite’s Metadata Schema, metadata meets one of the broadest cross-domain standards available.

Plan S - compliance self-assessment

The following Table is a self-assessment of Zenodo against the Plan S requirements for Open Access Repositories (as published October 2019). See the Plan S Principles and Implementation (under Part III: Technical Guidance and Requirements / 2. Requirements for Open Access Repositories).

Table 3. Mandatory (1-6) and strongly recommended (7-13) criteria for repositories vs. Zenodo

MANDATORY CRITERIA FOR REPOSITORIES		ZENODO
1. The repository must be registered in the Directory of Open Access Repositories (OpenDOAR) or in the process of being registered	✓	https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/id/repository/2659
2. Use of PIDs for the deposited versions of the publications (with versioning, for example, in case of revisions), such as DOI (preferable), URN, or Handle.	✓	Zenodo registers DOIs (via DataCite) for all deposited records. See DataCite. Zenodo pioneered DOI versioning Objects with pre-existing DOIs may be uploaded, and the external DOI displayed.

<p>3. High-quality article-level metadata in a standard interoperable nonproprietary format, under a CC0 public domain dedication. This must include information on the DOI (or other PIDs) both of the original publication and the deposited version, on the version deposited (AAM/VoR), and on the Open Access status and the license of the deposited version. Metadata must include complete and reliable information on funding provided by cOAlition S funders (including, as a minimum, the name of the funder and the grant number/identifier).</p>	<p>High-quality article-level metadata.” Zenodo supports the DataCite Metadata Schema v4. The following additional article level fields are supported: journal title/volume/issue/pages, conference title/acronym/dates/place/website, book publisher/place/ISBN/title/pages, alternate persistent identifiers (see all fields). “in the standard interoperable non-proprietary format.” The following metadata formats are provided by Zenodo: MARCXML, Dublin Core (according to OpenAIRE Guidelines), DataCite, DCAT, JSON-LD (Schema.org). “under a CC0 public domain dedication.” All metadata in Zenodo may be freely used under the CC0 waiver. (see terms of use, bullet 7).</p>
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	<p>“[...] include information on the DOI (or other PIDs) both of the original publication and the deposited version.” Zenodo registers DOIs for all uploads. Zenodo allows including information on alternate persistent identifiers, as well as linking to related persistent identifiers. “include [...] the Open Access status and the license of the deposited version.” All Zenodo records include the Open Access status according to the COAR access right vocabulary (open, embargoed, restricted, closed). All open access and embargoed records specify a license of the deposited material. Any license from the OpenDefinition and SPDX vocabularies are supported (including all Creative Commons licenses). “including as a minimum the name of the funder and the grant number/identifier.” All records can be uniquely linked to grants in the OpenAIRE grant database. The database currently covers 11 funders and 2 million grants.</p>
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<p>4. Machine-readable information on the Open Access status and the license embedded in the article in a standard non-proprietary format.</p>	<p>✓</p>	<p>The open-access status and a license are embedded in all metadata formats (i.e., machine-readable). See our APIs below in the strongly recommended criteria response.</p> <p>It is the responsibility of the uploader to ensure the open access status and a license is embedded in any digital file uploaded. Zenodo does not modify files uploaded by users in any way.</p>
<p>5. Continuous availability (uptime at least 99.7%, not taking into account scheduled downtime for maintenance or upgrades).</p>	<p>✓</p>	<p>Zenodo publicly displays uptime on https://status.zenodo.org Historically Zenodo's uptime is 99.98% (Oct 2019)</p>
<p>6. Helpdesk: as a minimum, an email address (functional mailbox) has to be provided; a response time of no more than one business day must be ensured.</p>	<p>✓</p>	<p>Zenodo provides support via https://zenodo.org/support The helpdesk is manned during CERN business hours (Mon-Fri 8:30-17:30 CET). Zenodo's average response time is 22 hours (based on 1534 requests received in the period May-Oct 2019, and not accounting for out-of-business hours).</p>
<p>7. Manuscript submission system that supports both individual author uploads and bulk uploads of</p>	<p>✓</p>	<p>Zenodo supports users/machines uploading both AAM and VoR versions of manuscripts.</p>
<p>manuscripts (AAM or VoR) by publishers.</p>		<p>Zenodo supports both author uploads via a normal deposit user interface as well as bulk uploads via our APIs.</p>
<p>8. Full text stored in a machinereadable community standard format such as JATS XML.</p>	<p>✓</p>	<p>Zenodo supports all file formats, consistent with the goal of accommodating all research objects. XML files are stored alongside other representations like PDF as just another format</p>
<p>9. Support for PIDs for authors (e.g., ORCID), funders, funding programs and grants, institutions, and other relevant entities.</p>	<p>✓</p>	<p>ORCID supported authors and contributors. Open Funder Registry supported funders. OpenAIRE grant database supported for grants. Zenodo plans to support ROR for institutions.</p>

<p>10. Openly accessible data on citations according to the standards by the Initiative for Open Citations (I4OC).</p>	<p>✓</p>	<p>Zenodo supports linking records with related persistent identifiers (both incoming and outgoing links - i.e., citations and references). The links are exported in the DataCite metadata registered with the DOI, and thus makes the links available in the CrossRef/DataCite Event Data.</p> <p>Discovering citations to a record requires global knowledge of the entire world-wide corpus of journal articles which is out of scope for Zenodo. Zenodo, however, harvests openly available citation databases (Crossref/DataCite Event Data, NASA/SAO Astrophysics Data System, and Europe PMC) for citations to Zenodo objects. All citation data is exported in Scholix-format. See https://help.zenodo.org/#citations for details.</p>
<p>11. Open API to allow others (including machines) to access the content. A compliant API must be free to access without any barrier. A light authentication mechanism such as a token for 'power users' – e.g., hightraffic collaborators – is acceptable as long as there is a totally open/anonymous route too.</p>	<p>✓</p>	<p>Available APIs: OAI-PMH: https://zenodo.org/oai2d REST API: https://zenodo.org/api/records/ Documentation: https://developers.zenodo.org Zenodo allows anonymous and authenticated access (via OAuth 2.0 access token) to the API. All requests to Zenodo (both UI and API) are ratelimited to prevent abusive use and DoS attacks (default limit: 5000 request/hour). Zenodo's average request rate is 14 requests/second.</p>
<p>12. OpenAIRE compliance of the metadata.</p>	<p>✓</p>	<p>Zenodo is compliant with the OpenAIRE Guidelines v3.0.</p>
<p>13. Quality assurance processes to link full-text deposits with authoritative bibliographic metadata from thirdparty systems, e.g., PubMed, Crossref, or SCOPUS, where feasible</p>	<p>✓</p>	<p>Per community harvesting allows curation and indexing, e.g., NASA ADS harvests specific communities which are curated by astronomy librarians; similarly by ZHB Luzern, BLR, etc.</p>

What naming conventions do you follow?

The general convention we will use is the following:

[WPx] [title] [year] [month] [verx] [.] ext

Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

yes

Do you provide clear version numbers?

CasProt uses a workspace where the individual versions are registered within the accepted rules of the Consortium.

Data Items: specification of metadata

The following data items are foreseen to be generated at this stage:

- a. Reports: metadata are included at the beginning of the same file.
- b. Presentations: Metadata is included at the end of the same file.
- c. Multimedia data: Metadata is included at the end of the same file.

All CasProt reports will display the following information within their 1.-3. page:

Name of project: Fostering high scientific quality in protein research in Eastern Slovakia (CasProt), No. 952333

Deliverable No:	
Work package no. and title::	
Task no. and title:	
Nature:	
Dissemination level:	
Lead Beneficiary:	
Author(s):	
Date of publication:	

Moreover, the file will report this sentence: This project has received funding from the European Union's H2020-WIDESPREAD-2018-2020 Twinning under grant agreement No 952333. Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the authors. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Union is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Database

Databases will be made available in .xlsx format. Metadata will follow the Dublin Core format

[2.] Following items will be included: content, Intellectual, Property, Instantiation, Title, Creator, Date, Subject, Publisher, Format, Description, Contributor, Identifier, Type Rights, Language, Source, Relation, Coverage. If not applicable for a particular item, NA abbreviation will be used.

In the first sheet (metadata), the following metadata will be available if possible (based on Dublin Core Format):

CALL	H2020-WIDESPREAD-2018-2020
WORK PROGRAMME	WIDESPREAD-03-2018: Twinning
Project ID	952333
Project web site	
Database type	Numeric, textual
Title	
Creator	
Contributors	
Publisher	
Date	
Format	
Status of the document	Draft / Final version
Draft version n.	
Identifier	

Each database will be provided with information about structure and content, as follows. In some cases, information on the quality of the data will be provided.

FIELD LABEL	DESCRIPTION	TYPE (NUMERIC, TEXT,Y,N)	FORMAT

Presentations

General information: Name of the project, Abbreviation of the project, nature of the meeting (e.g., Kick-off meeting), duration and date, presenter.

Multimedia

If applicable and possible, all multimedia products will contain CasProt logo, EU logo and reference to EU funding: *This project has received funding from the European Union's H2020-WIDESPREAD-2018-2020 Twinning under grant agreement No 952333.*

2.2 Making data openly accessible

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions.

In principle, most produced data will be openly available as the default, with two exceptions:

1. Research and other related data that can be a potential source of IPRs, as the public availability would jeopardize IPR evaluation processes, and
2. Internal communications with little relevance for outsiders. However, these data may be made available upon motivated request after anonymization.

A decision on whether particular data can be potentially used for IPR is solely on the researcher who conducted the experiment; if two and more researchers have participated in the experiment, a consensual decision has to be made.

How will the data be made accessible (e.g., by deposition in a repository)?

All CasProt data will be stored on the Zenodo repository after delivery to the REA. Before that moment, the data will be stored in the university servers and made accessible to all consortium members. Zenodo assigns a DOI to all documents uploaded and allows the storage of metadata.

It is expected that during the project CasProt running, the partnership EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) will be established and going into operation. The beneficiary's (UPJS) ambition is to be a key player in EOSC on behalf of the Slovak republic. In this case is expected that all scientific data generated by project CasProt will be managed, stored, standardized, registered, and cataloged in accordance with EOSC rules and adopted standards. This will stimulate cross-disciplinary and frontier science and help in implementing Goals in line with the policy of Open Science.

The European Open Science Cloud its new *modus operandi*, by providing standards, tools and services for open access to publications and data.

What methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g., in open source code)?

Most files will be accessible with general use software (word, excel, PowerPoint and their open versions). Successive versions of the DMP can be more specific for other types of data.

Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation, and code be deposited?

Preference should be given to certified repositories that support open access where possible. All CasProt data will be stored on the Zenodo repository after delivery to the REA.

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?

Yes

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?

The restriction is foreseen only for data generated by the internal social tool used by researchers within their particular workspace. They will be released upon approval of the data producers.

Is there a need for a data access committee?

No. Decision-making process for data access will be the competence of the project coordinator.

Are there well-described conditions for access (i.e., a machine-readable license)? How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

Conditions for the access will be specified in the next version of the DMP.

2.3 Making data interoperable

Are the data produced in the project interoperable, that is allowing data exchange and reuse between researchers, institutions, organizations, countries, etc. (i.e., adhering to standards

for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins)?

All metadata will refer to the Dublin Core. Moreover, we will make our metadata available following the OAI-PMH standard. The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) is a low-barrier mechanism for repository interoperability [3]. Data Providers are repositories that expose structured metadata via OAI-PMH. Service Providers then make OAI-PMH service requests to harvest that metadata. OAI-PMH is a set of six verbs or services that are invoked within HTTP. OAI-PMH will come for free if the decision is made to exploit the CasProt Catalogue service provided by Zenodo.

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

These are community-specific. A partial list of them should be included.

Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?

No.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

Mapping to most commonly used ontologies will be used only in monographs dedicated to general public.

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

CasProt reports will be licensed under Creative Commons license. The Creative Commons copyright licenses and tools forge a balance inside the traditional “all rights reserved” setting that copyright law creates. CC tools give everyone from individual creators to large companies and institutions a simple, standardized way to grant copyright permissions to creative work. The combination of CC tools and the users is a vast and growing digital commons, a pool of content that can be copied, distributed, edited, remixed, and built upon, all within the boundaries of copyright law [4].

When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

In general, data produced in the project will be made openly available as soon as the related deliverables are uploaded in the Project Portal.

Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.

Yes.

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable? Are data quality assurance processes described?

Data produced under CasProt project are accessible through Zenodo, open access repository. We expect these data remain re-usable. The data quality assurance process follows the rules of Zenodo.

3. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

3.1 What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project?

To make data FAIR, Zenodo will be chosen as the central open access repository. However, we expect that some research publications can be selected to be published under the 'golden' option.

3.2 How will these be covered? Note that costs related to open access to research data are eligible as part of the Horizon 2020 grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).

Costs for the making data FAIR will be covered from two resources: (1) other research grants (overheads/indirect costs/services), and (2) directly from the University (UPJS) budget.

3.3 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Data management is solved at the university level. As in the future, it is planned to create an appropriate working group at the university level. CassProt staff will work closely with this team.

3.4 Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?

The resources for long-term data preservation are covered by the UPJS.

4. DATA SECURITY

4.1 What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)?

Data are collected and stored in the CasProt workspace, and then data are sent to the Zenodo repository. This repository is protected with Transport Level Security (TLS) that offers communications security over the computer network. TLS guarantees privacy and data integrity between two communicating PC applications. In particular, any connections between a client (e.g., a web browser) and the CasProt workspace have the following properties:

- a. The connection is private (or secure) due to the adoption of symmetric cryptography to encrypt the data transmitted. The keys for this symmetric encryption are generated uniquely for each connection and are based on a shared secret negotiated at the start of the session. The server and client negotiate the details of which encryption algorithm and cryptographic keys to use before the first byte of data is transmitted. The negotiation of a shared secret is both secure (the negotiated secret is unavailable to eavesdroppers and cannot be obtained, even by an attacker who places themselves in the middle of the connection) and reliable (no attacker can modify the communications during the negotiation without being detected)
- b. The identity of the communicating parties can be authenticated using public-key cryptography. This authentication can be made optional at the client side but is ensured at the server-side
- c. The connection ensures integrity because each message transmitted includes a message integrity check using a message authentication code to prevent undetected loss or alteration of the data during transmission
- d. The connection ensures forward secrecy, ensuring that any future disclosure of encryption keys cannot be used to decrypt any TLS communications recorded in the past.

To protect CasProt data from various scenarios of data loss incidents, a backup and recovery strategy has been developed. The most probable data loss incidents can be divided into three categories [5]:

- 1) physical destruction of hardware such as server nodes and other related critical infrastructure due to *force majeure* or simply due to defective components
- 2) human error
- 3) viruses, malware, or ransomware

To prevent data loss incidents, such as that data are deleted accidentally, CasProt work package leaders are asked to keep the data copies using their individual storage modules or cloud systems. According to statistics, notebooks are less suitable for long-term storage [5].

The CasProt workspace provides continuous, online backup for data as a fully managed service. The service streams encrypted and compressed oplog data to a dedicated server so that a continuous backup is activated.

4.2 Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

5. ETHICAL ASPECTS

5.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA). Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

According to the Grant Agreement, the main ethical issues for CasProt are +research involving human beings and the protection of personal data. All the internal procedures needed to assure compliance with the requirements have been so far developed in the following tasks:

- Task 7.1.: H- Ethics requirement No. 1
This task aims to prepare informed consent procedures that will be implemented for the participation of humans in specific surveys. Prepared templates of the informed consents and information sheets (in language and terms intelligible to the participants) will be kept on file. The documents to be kept on file will be submitted upon request by the coordinator to the REA.
- Task 7.2.: POPD – Ethics requirement No. 2
In this task, a description of the technical and organizational measures that will be implemented to safeguard the data subjects/research participant’s rights and freedom will be addressed. The documents to be kept on file will be submitted upon request by the coordinator to the REA.
- Task 7.3.: EPQ - Ethics requirement No. 3
Regarding the possible work and staff training involving strains of *Escherichia coli*, we will prepare health and safety procedures for staff involved conforming to relevant local/national guidelines. The relevant document will be kept in a file and, upon request, submitted to the REA.

These tasks yield the following deliverables: D7.1. Template of the informed consent (M03), D7.2. Preparation of the data technical and organizational measures (M03), D7.3. Health and safety procedure for work with *Escherichia coli* (M03). These three deliverables further detail the procedures of information of research participants already included in the Grant Agreement, to guarantee that prior to the collection of any data, participants will be informed on the collection, processing, and use of data provided and that contact persons of the Consortium will ensure that they give the consent (D. 7.1). Research activities interested in ethics requirements in each Work Package are detailed in Deliverable 7.1, together with a list of actions to be taken in order to guarantee compliance. D.7.1 reports the information sheet

and the informed consent statement, which includes details about data collection, data use, data analysis, data storage, and long term preservation, data anonymization, and the right to withdraw the participation. Deliverable 7.2 “POPD – Requirement N.2”, due at month 12 of the Project, will report the confirmation of the appointment of a Data Protection Officer by the beneficiaries, as well as the organizational measures. Prior to any work with bacterial strains, the staff will be informed on health and safety procedures for work with *Escherichia coli* (D.7.3).

6. FURTHER SUPPORT IN DEVELOPING YOUR DMP

The DMP will be updated based on *ad hoc* requirements collected during the project. Data management policies as defined in this version of the DMP will be evaluated by the project coordinator, who is also responsible for further development of a regular update of the DMP.

7. REFERENCES

[1] Wilkinson, M. D. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci. Data* 3:160018 doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18 (2016).

[2] <https://www.dublincore.org/>

[3] <https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/>

[4] <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/>

[5] <https://blog.storagecraft.com/data-loss-statistics-infographic>

In Košice on May 10th, 2022

Approved by: Erik Sedlák

